

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Jones**FIRST NAME:** Danine**PROGRAM CODE:** DILT**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **A researcher chooses the pragmatism paradigm to shape his/her research question and to determine how he/she will undertake his/her research because:**
 - This paradigm allows the researcher to construct a remedy to his research question through a research methodology that takes into account the principles and values of his/her research subjects.
 - This type of research would change the lives of the research subjects, the communities in which they live and their institutions through reforms identified by the research.
 - He/she wants to test and verify the norms, laws and principles which govern the way in which his/her research subjects live and carry out their daily activities.
 - The researcher believes that his/her research question should shape his/her methodology and that it is appropriate to combine more than one method in order to better understand the research**

- question. This paradigm will allow him/her to decide whether it is best to include research subjects in his research.¹**
2. **“My thesis proposes to demonstrate that risk is one of the more significant features of corporate law.” This is an inappropriate research proposal because it:**
- Frames the thesis proposal in the past.
 - The research proposal is too wide making it difficult for the researcher to define the problem he/she wishes to research.
 - It does not describe how the problem will be addressed.
 - All of the above.²**
3. **Why should a researcher start reading the literature which concerns his/her topic as early as possible and make notes about what he or she finds?**
- To force the student to read numerous pieces of writing on a topic so that the student understands that undertaking a research degree is a difficult pursuit.
 - To provide the researcher with the opportunity to observe and understand what has already been written on his/her topic of interest.³**
 - To assist the researcher in defining the limitations of his area of study.
 - To give the researcher an opportunity to identify a possible research sample early.

¹ Linda Bloomberg and Maria Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (California: Sage Publication Inc, 2008), 74.

² Bloomberg and Volpe, 18-19.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 47.

4. **Turabian described seven principles of writing proper sentences. Which one of these statements is a principle identified by Turabian?**

- As far as possible begin most of your sentences with the subject.**⁴
- The verb which describes what the noun is doing should be placed as far away as possible from the noun it addresses.
- It is unnecessary to describe unfamiliar information with introductory words since a research thesis is supposed to introduce the reader to information, he/she has never been exposed to before.
- When stating an opinion ensure that the words “In my opinion” are stated so that the reader understands that the opinion of the researcher is being stated and not that of another source.

5. **To avoid plagiarising someone else’s work, Turabian advises that direct quotations can be used. However which statement is correct in relation to direct quotations?**

- Using direct quotations is preferable to paraphrasing.
- Use direct quotations to increase the credibility and professionalism of your writing as it illustrates that you have carefully read and noted your sources.
- When quoting four lines or less, direct quotations can form a part of the text. However, where direct quotations are longer than four lines, block quotations should be used.**⁵
- Always use the introductory words “The author stated” or “[name of author] stated” prior to using a direct quotation.

6. **Turabian recommends that sub-headings be used when writing, especially when one is doing a complex assignment because it is:**

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 74.

⁵ Turabian, 208.

- Aesthetically pleasing to the eye and gives the reader a break from continuous paragraphs.
 - Enables the researcher to keep his or her writing on track.**⁶
 - It facilitates better understanding of what is written.
 - The use of sub-headings would allow the reader to present a more detailed table of contents which shows that the researcher is thoughtful about his/her readers.
7. **According to Bluebook, where should a footnote call number appear in a textual sentence?**
- At the end of the entire sentence.
 - Only next to the portion of the sentence it supports or contradicts and after the punctuation mark.**⁷
 - At the end of the sentence if it supports or contradicts it but before the punctuation mark.
 - At the end of the portion of the sentence it supports or contradicts but before any punctuation marks in the sentence.
8. **Turabian advises readers that “normal panic”, which can set in when engaging in complex writing tasks, can be managed by:**
- Breaking larger tasks into smaller more manageable tasks and creating journals recording what has been read.**⁸
 - Only read sources that you feel comfortable reading because these will be easier to understand thereby providing more ease when doing the Literature Review.

⁶ Turabian, 45.

⁷ *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th ed. (Cambridge Massachusetts: Columbia Law Review, Harvard Law Review, University of Pennsylvania Law Review: Harvard Law Review University Press., n.d.), 53.

⁸ Turabian, 35.

- Organise all sources into specific categories and read each category at a time thus giving yourself adequate space in between to assimilate the information properly.
- Using key words in your notes and sorting the notes under those specific key words.

9. **The ISO 8601 standard for writing dates is:**

- 11th October, 2020.
- October 11, 2020.
- October the 11th 2020..
- 2020-10-11.**⁹

10. **A researcher does not have to cite everything. In what circumstances should you not cite?**

- When quoting from the Bible.
- When the information is common knowledge.**¹⁰
- If the information being cited is taken from a television programme.
- When using information that was authored by you in a previous work.

⁹ Laurent Cleenerwerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D CoursePack Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 35.

¹⁰ Cleenerwerck and Gulma, 10.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda, and Maria Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation A Roadmap From Beginning to End*. California: Sage Publication Inc, 2008.
- Cleenerwerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D CoursePack Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*. 19th ed. Cambridge Massachusetts: Columbia Law Review, Harvard Law Review, University of Pennsylvania Law Review: Harvard Law Review University Press., n.d.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.
- .

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.